

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Country Dossier Iran - WP4

Governance of Return Migration from Iran to Afghanistan: An Overview of Return Infrastructure and Institutional Environment

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List of abbreviations

AVR	Assisted Voluntary Return
BAFIA	Bureau of Aliens and Foreign Immigrants
EU	European Union
IDPs	Internally Displaced Persons
IOM	International Organization for Migration
MOFA	Ministry of Foreign Affairs
MoI	Ministry of Interior
MoRR	Ministry of Refugee and Repatriation
N-AVR	National Assisted Voluntary Return
NOM	National Organization for Migration
NRC	Norwegian Refugee Council
PMM	Presidency of Migration Management
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
UN	United Nations
UN	United States

Summary

The Islamic Republic of Iran hosts the largest population of Afghan refugees worldwide. However, recent years have seen significant dynamics in both inflow and outflow, highlighting the complexities of return migration governance. While estimates vary, with the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) suggesting around 4.5 million Afghans in Iran and the Iranian government indicating over 5 million, the International Organization for Migration (IOM) recorded a substantial out-migration of 8.99 million from Afghanistan to Iran between 2021 and 2023, with 7.97 million returns from Iran and Afghanistan recorded during the same period.¹

Multiple factors drive this migration pattern, including political upheaval post-regime change in August 2021, socio-economic strains exacerbated by disruptions in international aid, and societal norms impacting women's inclusion in education and employment. Notably, the UNHCR reports a spike in daily crossings from Afghanistan to Iran, jumping from 2,000 to 5,000 between August and September 2021.²

Despite Iran's commitment to international refugee conventions, data on Afghan asylum seekers and recognized refugees seeking protection in Iran remain very limited. Iran's governance of return migration reflects a nuanced response shaped by socio-political dynamics, economic realities, and diplomatic relations with Afghanistan and the broader international community. This underscores the evolving nature of return migration governance and the need for comprehensive approaches to address the diverse challenges and opportunities it presents. This report assesses Iran's approach to return migration governance, examining the factors that contributed to the development of return migration infrastructure and influenced Iran's changing return migration diplomacies. Additionally, it sheds light on Afghanistan's return and reintegration approaches, policy frameworks and legal documents.

¹ For more about cross-border movement between Afghanistan and its neighboring countries see IOM report on Afghanistan Cross-Border Mobility Report: Two Years of Mixed Migration Review, available at https://roasiapacific.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd1671/files/documents/2024-02/05022023_afg_2y_cross-border-mobility-report.pdf.

² For detail see UNCHR (2022), 'Afghanistan Situation: Regional Refugee Response Plan', https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/EN_23.pdf, p. 16.

GAPs Project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by de-centring the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policymaking.” To this end, GAPs:

- examine the shortcomings of EU’s return governance;
- analyse enablers and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explore the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its decentring approach with three innovative concepts:

- a focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance fissures;
- an analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU Member States and with third countries hinder cooperation on return; and
- a trajectory approach that uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is an interdisciplinary 3-year project (2023-2026), co-coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies with 17 partners in 12 countries on 4 continents. GAPs' fieldwork has been conducted in 14 countries: Jordan, Lebanon, Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq.

This country dossier has been compiled in the context of the GAPs Work Package on ‘Return Migration Governance in the African and Middle Eastern Regions and the Role of the EU.’

Since the vast majority of migrants and refugees move and reside in and among countries in the immediate region of their origin countries, return migration will also predominantly take place within the region of countries in crisis. Yet, scholarly concerns have overwhelmingly focused on the minority of migrants who travelled further afield, in particular to the European Union, and return from there to their regions of origin. Relatively little attention has been given to return policies of neighbouring receiving states in the Global South.

Disregarding this regional dimension puts a Eurocentric bias on the study of return migration governance. Regional return governance, moreover, both shapes and is shaped by the externalization and return migration policies of the EU. On the one hand, the EU’s deterrence and externalization ‘partnerships’ fundamentally affect return diplomacies, infrastructures, and trajectories in its neighbouring regions. On the other hand, the governance of regional returns has repercussions the migration dynamics the EU seeks to control, for its engagement with ‘third countries,’ and for the international norms it claims to uphold.

To address this knowledge gap, therefore, this Work Package has the aim to better understand the intersections between (i) return migration governance within the African and Middle Eastern regions and (ii) the role of the European Union and its external migration policy. To this end, it asks three core research questions: (i) What characterizes return migration governance within African and Middle Eastern regions? Specifically: how are these modalities

shaped by the EU's external migration policy?; (ii) What are the driving forces behind these types of return migration governance? Specifically: how are these drivers affected by the EU's external migration policy?; and (iii) What are the effects of these drivers and modalities of regional migration governance, for both people and policy? Specifically: what are the implications of specific regional return migration governance for the EU's external migration policy? The Work Package answers these questions for eight 'host countries' (Iraq, Jordan, Lebanon, Türkiye, Iran, Morocco, Tunisia, Libya) focused on three 'origin countries' (Syria, Afghanistan, Nigeria).

Research in this Work Package is carried out in an embedded-multiple case study design, in which cases are selected for diversity (encompassing variation in return types) and representativeness (including main host countries in return systems that are salient to Europe, i.e., Africa, the broader Middle East). Data are generated through document analysis (a minimum of 20 documents – including academic papers, expert report, and media coverage – has been analyzed in-depth per country dossier) and 10 (semi-structured, in-depth) expert interviews (with state authorities, international organizations, and civil society actors) have been conducted. Data was coded iteratively. First deductively, through a common codebook based on a shared conceptual framework developed to answer the three core questions listed above. Particular attention here is paid to modalities (legal, policy and operational infrastructures), drivers (capacity and interests of actors), and outcomes (monitoring mechanisms and expert views on sustainability of returns). Second, data was coded inductively, highlighting emerging themes that were not included in the codebook but that nevertheless surfaced as contextually relevant. Research has been subject to ethical review of the host institutions of the individual researchers conducting the country-specific research. The core concern here has been to ensure (oral) informed consent for interviews on the basis of full anonymity of interlocutors. Document and interview analysis have been synthesized through two workshops dedicated to these specific research phases.

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While the governance of return migration from Iran to Afghanistan has long been inconsistent and shaped by a shifting geostrategic and political landscape, this report offers meaningful insight into the institutional environment, evolving policy narratives, and a brief historical analysis of return migration governance between the two countries.

An empirical analytical approach has been employed, combining primary data collection with a review of credible academic, policy-oriented, and legal secondary sources. Throughout the analysis, particular attention has been paid to ethical considerations and the principles of international human rights law, which have served as guiding frameworks to ensure the integrity, fairness, and human-centered nature of the research.

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1. Introduction

Despite being a party to the 1951 Convention Relating to the Status of the Refugees and its 1967 Protocol,³ there is no data available on Iran regarding Afghan asylum seekers undergoing Refugee Status Determination and recognized refugees who seek international protection.⁴ Iran's reaction, response and policies toward Afghan refugees varied greatly according to its sociopolitical and economic situations including its relations with the government of Afghanistan and the international community.

After forty-four years since the initial arrival of Afghans in 1979, the management of Afghan refugees in Iran continues to present a complex, multifaceted challenge. This complex issue encompasses a broad spectrum of challenges across multiple levels, spanning socio-political, legal, integration, and the broader principles of return migration governance.

The first institutional approach to return Afghan migrants back to their homeland began in the early 1990s. The first action at the institutional level was to stop registering new arrivals in the country.⁵ At regional level, the government signed the first repatriation Tripartite Agreement between Afghanistan, Iran and UNHCR in 1992.⁶ The return migration process characterized by incremental measures, the government of Iran systematically curtailed the scope of public services extended to registered Afghan refugees. Specifically, this entailed the denial of fundamental provisions such as access to education and healthcare services,⁷ thereby exacerbating the socio-economic challenges and forcing the Afghan migrants to return to Afghanistan. As a result, in 1993, about 600,000 Afghans returned from Iran to Afghanistan.⁸

The civil war that unfolded in Afghanistan throughout the 1990s, characterised by the protracted conflict between the Soviet-backed regime and a diverse array of over half a dozen Pakistan- and Iran-based Islamic factions, constituted a pivotal chapter in the nation's political history. This period witnessed the convergence of geopolitical interests, with various state and non-state actors lending support to opposing factions, thereby exacerbating the already volatile situation. This instability not only resulted in widespread internal displacement but also triggered a significant surge in outward migration from Afghanistan. In other words, the second wave of forced out-migration, driven by the grim realities of war and political upheaval, underscored the profound impact of conflict dynamics on population movements towards Iran and the broader region.

Migration pressure from Afghanistan has been testing the institutional and operational capacities of the Iranian government. To illuminate the evolving institutional and operational behaviours of Iran's return migration governance, this report offers a retrospective assessment of Iran's return migration infrastructure and governance. Furthermore, it presents a comprehensive overview of return migration and reintegration governance in Afghanistan.

³ For details visit <https://www.unhcr.org/protect/PROTECTION/3b73bod63.pdf>

⁴ See UNHCR Global Appeal 2010-11, visit <https://www.unhcr.org/4b03cdc39.pdf>

⁵ See Human Rights Watch (2013), 'Unwelcome Guests: Iran's Violation of Afghan Refugee and Migrant Rights', <https://www.hrw.org/report/2013/11/20/unwelcome-guests/irans-violation-afghan-refugee-and-migrant-rights>.

⁶ See European Union for Asylum's (EUAA) Country of Origin Information on Iran – Situation of Afghan refugees (2022), https://euaa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/publications/2023-01/2023_01_COI_Report_Iran_Afghans_Refugees_EN.pdf, p. 17.

⁷ See Hugo, G., Abbasi-Shavazi, M. J. and Sadeghi, R. (2012), 'Refugee Movement and Development – Afghan Refugees in Iran', *Migration and Development*, Vol. 1 No. 2, 261-279, p. 267.

⁸ Abbasi-Shavazi, M. J., Glazebrook, D. J., Gholamreza, M. H. and Sadeghi, R. (2005) 'Return to Afghanistan?: A Study of Afghans Living in Zahedan, Islamic Republic of Iran'. *Afghanistan Research and Evaluation Unit (AREU)*, <https://www.refworld.org/reference/countryrep/areu/2005/en/55479>

Additionally, it evaluates the effects of the Iranian government's approach to return migration on the Afghan government's return and reintegration governance, juxtaposed with the impacts of out-migration pressure on Iran's return migration governance. In summary, this report examines micro, meso, and macro-level factors that have influenced return migration and reintegration governance in both Iran and Afghanistan.

2. Methods

This report is based on a mixed method of primary and secondary data analysis. To understand the development of return migration governance in Iran and reintegration institutional initiatives in Afghanistan, it has reviewed a broad array of secondary sources encompassing articles, books, policy reports, legal documents, including published and unpublished government reports, and mediatic discourses. The report also utilizes quantitative survey and in-depth life-history interviews with returnees from Iran conducted between December 2023 and January 2024 and expert panel discussions and unstructured group discussions with government officials, non-governmental officials, and academics in Türkiye, including officials from the Ministry of Refugee and Repatriation, Afghanistan between April and May 2024.

3. Context

Initial drivers of outmigration from the country under study

In 2023, Afghanistan ranked 2nd in producing the highest number of refugees worldwide.⁹ The Soviet invasion of Afghanistan in 1979 and subsequent waves of internal conflicts, and violence along with recurrent natural disasters forced over 6 million Afghans to remain forcibly displaced outside their country.¹⁰ The majority of Afghan migrants end up seeking refuge in neighbouring countries. For example, with over 4.5 million the Islamic Republic of Iran (the number of Afghan migrants according to Iranian officials is 5.5 million in the country¹¹) hosts the largest population of Afghan migrants globally. Iran has not only been one of the main destinations for millions of displaced Afghan population for nearly five decades, but it also has been one of the favourite transit destinations to reach Türkiye and Europe¹². According to IOM, the migration corridor between Afghanistan and Iran is the 7th largest in the world.¹³ This signifies a substantial migration flow between these two countries, ranking it as the seventh largest migration corridor globally in terms of both volume and scale.

⁹ See UNHCR Refugee Statistics at <https://www.unhcr.org/refugee-statistics/>

¹⁰ Ibid

¹¹ Kazimi, S. M. M. (2022), What the Current Research Say about Afghan Refugee (پژوهش ها در باره مهاجرین (افغانستانی چه می گویند؟), *The Islamic Republic News Agency*, 27 May 2022.

¹² RadioFreeEurope (2018) 'Turkey Face 'New Refugee Wave' After Nearly 30,000 Afghans Arrive', <https://www.rferl.org/a/turkey-faces-new-refugee-wave-after-nearly-30-000-afghans-arrive/29191918.html>

¹³ See IOM World Migration Report (2022), p. 27, <https://publications.iom.int/books/world-migration-report-2022>

With a 936-kilometre-long border, Iran is one of the most important neighbours of Afghanistan and has strong cultural, ethnic, linguistic, and religious ties with Afghanistan.¹⁴ Both countries experienced political revolutions between 1978 and 1979. In Afghanistan, after a mass uprising in April 1978 so-called the Saur Revolution (April Revolution), the time's President, Mohammad Daud Khan was killed in a communist coup d'état. In Iran, the Islamic Revolution in February 1979 brought Ayatollah Ruhollah Khomeini to power.¹⁵ Following the establishment of the Islamic Republic, Iran's policy on Afghanistan was largely shaped by Khomeini's Islamic ideology – Islamic solidarity¹⁶.

With the onset of the Cold War in South Asia, Afghanistan's internal political and ethnic issues were exposed on the international stage.¹⁷ The religiously motivated wars so called *jihad* accentuated by external forces (Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, and the West including the United States) had gained political momentum and transformed political discrepancies into military warfare across the country. The civil war ravaged and destructed mass populated rural areas (80% of the population lived in rural areas¹⁸) forcing over 400,000 Afghans to outmigration, particularly to Pakistan and Iran.¹⁹

As the war expanded and escalated on various fronts and the situation severely deteriorated on several parameters, a greater number of Afghans were forced to outmigration. The turning point within this context came when the Soviets invaded Afghanistan in 1979. Within a year over six million Afghans were forced to leave their country.²⁰

Arrival and Reception in Host Countries: Numbers, Socio-economic and Political Reactions

Iran's institutional response to the Afghan refugee crisis remained inconsistent and changed relevant to the changing social, economic, political and security situations including its relationship with the Afghan government and international community. For instance, Iran adopted a *prima facie* policy, a friendly approach, towards the acceptance of Afghan asylum seekers in 1979. Iran's *prima facie* policy towards Afghan refugees between 1979 and the late 1980s was concordant with Ayatollah Ruhollah Khomeini's principles of Islamic solidarity. In other words, "Iran felt obligated" to offer protection to Afghan asylum seekers.²¹ The Iranian government's policy towards Afghan refugees was replete with reference to Ayatollah Khomeini's ideology of the Islamic community that dismissed nationalism in the Islamic world – the border between Islamic countries.²² Despite religious differences, Iran's regional political interest was to promote the concept of pan-Islamism, aiming to unite Muslim nations against both capitalist and communist ideologies. According to Koepke, a fundamental tenet

¹⁴ For details see Koepke, B. (2013), *Iran's Policy on Afghanistan: The Evolution of Strategic Pragmatism*, Stockholm: Sipri, p.1

¹⁵ Ibid

¹⁶ Kasimis, D. (2019), 'Response to Yabakhsh Elisabeth. Reading Derrida in Tehran: Between an Open Door and Empty *Sofreh*.', *Humanities*, Vol 4, No. 140., p.2. also see Koepke (2013), p.3.

¹⁷ See Gupta, B. S. (1986) *Afghanistan Politics, Economics and Society*, London: Frances Publishers Ltd. P. 3.

¹⁸ See Samady, S. R. (2001) "Education and Afghan Society in the Twentieth Century", United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, Education Sector, <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0012/001246/124627E.pdf>, 10–29., 14

¹⁹ See Rizvi, H. A. (First Quarter 1984), "Afghan Refugees in Pakistan: Influx, Humanitarian Assistance and Implications," *Pakistan Horizon* 37, no.1, P. 42.

²⁰ See Valentina, H. (2014) 'Repatriation of Afghan Refugees in Pakistan; Voluntary?', *Oxford Monitor of Forced Migration* 4/1, p. 42.

²¹ Koepke (2013), p.4

²² Kasimis, D. (2019), 'Response to Yabakhsh Elisabeth. p.2. Also see Koepke (2013), p.3.

of Iranian ideology was the vision of exporting the Islamic revolution.²³ However, during the early and late 1980s, Iran was deeply preoccupied with two major crises—the 1979–81 hostage crisis at the American embassy in Tehran and the Iran-Iraq War from 1980–88—leaving little room to develop a comprehensive strategy for Afghanistan.²⁴

Although Iranian officials implemented an open-door policy towards the first waves of Afghan influx, institutionally they lacked the required infrastructure to manage the growing number of asylum seekers in the country. The number of refugees inflow from Afghanistan between 1980 and 1981 was about 6,000 people a day.²⁵ By November 1981 the number of Afghan refugees in Iran reached 1.5 million people.²⁶ This situation forced Iranian officials to unconditionally allow Afghan refugees to settle in the cities. However, policies allowing Afghan refugee settlements in Iranian societies have had dramatic repercussions on the overall situation of Afghans in Iran. The economic and social burden (such as job market pressure, increased public expenditures, and religio-cultural tensions) caused by the influx of millions of Afghans in a short period of time negatively impacted the public perception of Afghan refugees. To jettison the refugee burden, in the late 1980s, particularly after the collapse of the Soviet-backed regime in Kabul in 1992, the Iranian government started to implement non-integration restrictive policies to force Afghans to return to their home country.²⁷ In this context, the first formal repatriation programme for Afghans was initiated under the Tripartite Agreement between Iran, Afghanistan and the UNHCR.²⁸ From 1992, the Iranian government increased its efforts to send Afghans back by denying registration to new arrivals without clear reasons and limiting their freedom of movement.²⁹

Moreover, the Iran – Iraq war and soaring unfriendly relations with the Western world, (isolation from the international system) were some of the other key factors that negatively impacted the development of institutional infrastructure to manage the refugee crisis. Furthermore, the strained relations between Iran and the Western world have markedly hindered Iran's interactions with Western-supported United Nations migration regimes. This adversarial dynamic has erected significant barriers to cooperation and meaningful engagement with these international bodies. The deep-seated mistrust and political tensions between Iran and Western nations have fostered a reluctance on Iran's part to fully participate in or endorse the initiatives and policies promoted by these UN migration regimes. Consequently, the opportunities for collaborative efforts to address migration challenges were curtailed, further complicating the global management of migration issues. This marked a significant divergence from internationally recognized frameworks, procedures and aid regarding refugee management and settlements. For example, in the context of financial aid, while Pakistan (home to nearly 3.2 million Afghan refugees in 1990³⁰) received over US\$848

²³ Keopke (2013), p.4

²⁴ Keopke (2013), pp. 3-4.

²⁵ See Goodson, L. P (2001), *Afghanistan's Endless War: State failure, Regional Politics, and the Rise of the Taliban*, United States: University of Washington Press, p.149.

²⁶ See Esfahani, A. N. and Hosseini, H. (2018), 'Afghan Refugees and Iran's Open Door Policy in the 1980s', *Pertanika Journal Social Science and Humanity*, 26 (T), pp. 235-252.

²⁷ Goodson (2001),149.

²⁸ EUAA (2022), p.17.

²⁹ For details see EUAA report.

³⁰ For details see report on "Timeline of Afghan Displacement into Pakistan" at visit

<https://reliefweb.int/report/pakistan/timeline-afghan-displacements-pakistan#:~:text=1980%3A%20UNHCR%20sets%20up%20its,an%20estimated%20500%2C000%20unregisteredd%20refugees.>

million in funds from the UNHCR between 1979 and 1990, Iran (home to nearly 3 million Afghan refugees in 1991³¹) during the same period received a total of US\$ 102,822,700.³²

Concordant to political upheaval in Afghanistan, Iran's Afghan refugee policies remained highly inconsistent since the 1990s. The next section of the report explores Iran's governance of return migration in the period following 1992. The following table summarises some major events in Afghanistan and their impacts on Iran's Afghan refugee policies between 1979 and 2021 (see Table 1).

Phase/Date	Political Environment	Number of Outmigration	Iran's Policy Response
Phase-I 1979-89	Soviet Invasion of Afghanistan	2,350,000 ³³	- <i>Open door policy, prima facie</i> - <i>Humanitarian response Provision of refugee identification cards, so-called Blue Card</i>
Phase-II 1990-94	Civil War	2,940,000 ³⁴	<i>Refusal to register new arrivals in 1992</i> ³⁵
Phase -III 1994-2001	The Emergence of the Taliban	1,480,000 ³⁶	- <i>In 1997 officially stopped granting a residence permit</i> - <i>In 2000 Article 48, established the parameter of deportation</i> ³⁷
Phase -IV 2001-2021	The United States (US) led the Invasion	1,400,000	- <i>In 2003 re-registration of documented Afghan refugees was initiated, called the Amayesh system</i>
Phase – V 2021 present	Post-American Retreat and re-emergence of the Taliban rule	5,000,000 Afghans live in Iran. ³⁸	- <i>Forced deportation</i> - <i>Restrictions imposed on Afghan workers</i>

³¹ Abbasi-Shavazi and Glazebrook (2006)

³² Eisenberger, J. (2013), *The Boatless People: The UNHCR and Afghan Refugees, 1978-1989*, *Department of International History, Graduate Institute of International and Development Studies*, Working Paper in International History, No.14., p.15

³³ Eisenberger (2013) p.14

³⁴ Goodson (2001) p.148

³⁵ For detail see Human Rights Watch (2013), 'Unwelcome Guests: Iran's Violation of Afghan Refugee and Migrant Rights', <https://www.hrw.org/report/2013/11/20/unwelcome-guests/irans-violation-afghan-refugee-and-migrant-rights>, Accessed on 4 April 4, 2022.

³⁶ For details visit

<https://www.refworld.org/docid/3b31e164f.html#:~:text=Iran%20continued%20to%20host%20about,Iraqis%2C%20and%20about%2026%2C000%20others.>

³⁷ Ibid

³⁸ Embassy of Islamic Republic of Iran's official webpage at <https://kabul.mfa.ir/portal/newsview/676017>

Domestic (Social, economic and /or political conditions) and External Factors (regional and inter-state political situations)

Until 1992 the government of Iran unconditionally granted Afghans arriving in the country the right to stay and provided them with Identity Cards (Blue Cards), which acknowledged that they were refugees (*Muhajerin*) but did not legally authorise refugee status to Afghans.³⁹ However, after 1992 with the fall of the Soviet-supported regime in Kabul Iran's policy towards Afghan refugees has dramatically changed. The Iranian government officially stopped the registration of newly arriving Afghans in the country.⁴⁰ Moreover, the government incrementally reduced public services to registered Afghan refugees.⁴¹ Particularly, Afghan refugees were denied education and health services.⁴² During this period, Iran also launched its first return policy by signing the Tripartite Commission with Afghanistan, and the UNHCR⁴³ that focused on return.

With the installation of the US-backed interim government after the collapse of the Taliban regime in 2001, the Iranian government revised the Tripartite Agreement with the UNHCR and Afghanistan extending the voluntary return of Afghans to their country.⁴⁴ With the introduction of the *Amayesh* (logistic or preparation) registration system⁴⁵, a new policy was put in place to manage the Afghan refugee crisis in the country. The *Amayesh* registration cards have replaced all other previously issued documents for Afghan asylum seekers.⁴⁶ To renew the *Amayesh* card each Afghan asylum seeker had to pay up to US\$ 200 municipal tax and US\$ 15 to renew their refugee status.⁴⁷ Since its launch, the Iranian authorities have provided 16 rounds of *Amayesh* cards.⁴⁸ The cards had a different colour each time and their validity varied from three months to one year.⁴⁹ That said, the information recorded has remained different in each round.

The *Amayesh* card allows access to education, but it does not mean that all Afghan children attend school.⁵⁰ Because most of the Afghans were unable to pay their children's education fees. One year of school education per head cost an average of US\$ 150 in 2004.⁵¹ During this period at least three factors were highly influential in shaping Iran's Afghan return policies. Firstly, domestic socio-cultural tensions between Afghan asylum seekers and Iranian citizens – for example, societal discrimination based on legal status and economic power, as well as

³⁹ Human Rights Watch (2013), 'Unwelcome Guests: Iran's Violation of Afghan Refugee and Migrant Rights', <https://www.hrw.org/report/2013/11/20/unwelcome-guests/irans-violation-afghan-refugee-and-migrant-rights>, p.32

⁴⁰ Ibid

⁴¹ Ibid

⁴² Hugo, G., Abbasi-Shavazi, and Sadeghi (2012), 267.

⁴³ Human Rights Watch (2013), p.33, also see Abbasi-Shavazi, Glazebrook, Jamshidiha, Mahmoudian, H. and Sadeghi, (2005), 'Return to Afghanistan? A study of Afghans Living in Mashhad, Islamic Republic of Iran, *Afghanistan Research and Evaluation Unit*, <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/C5B61D78C2837165492570980023044B-areu-afg-12oct.pdf>,

⁴⁴ Ibid

⁴⁵ Human Rights Watch (2013), p.32

⁴⁶ See Naseh, M., Potocky, M., Stuart, P.H., and Pezeshk, S. (2018), 'Repatriation of Afghan refugees from Iran: a shelter profile study', *Int J Humanitarian Action* 3, 13.

⁴⁷ Ibid

⁴⁸ For details visit <https://reliefweb.int/report/iran-islamic-republic/unhcr-iran-announcement-amayesh-16-registration>

⁴⁹ Human Rights Watch (2013), p.33-34.

⁵⁰ See the Report published by the Landinfo on Afghan Citizen in Iran (2011) at https://landinfo.no/asset/2063/1/2063_1.pdf,

⁵¹ Ibid

religious tensions between Sunni Afghan migrants and Shia Iranians - have played an important role in shaping Iran's fluctuating return policies towards Afghan refugees. These policies, shaped by heightened discrimination against Afghans have resulted in the restriction of Afghan asylum seekers' socio-cultural rights across multiple tiers such as freedom of movement, forced deportation, limited access to education, right to job and economic opportunities, right to marriage with Iranian citizen. Second, Iran's relations with the Western world, particularly with the US, along with Afghanistan's political and strategic connections with Western powers, have significantly influenced Iran's return policies. The US–Afghanistan strategic and security partnership agreements have been key factors that influenced Iran's refugee policy toward Afghans. For example, while objecting to the Security Pact, signed between Afghanistan and the US, the Iranian government threatened to expel Afghan refugees from the country.⁵² This action served as a means for Iran to express its disapproval of Afghanistan's decision to align with the US, which Iran views as a hostile power. By leveraging the presence of Afghan refugees, Iran sought to exert pressure on Afghanistan to conform to its national interests. This strategy underscores how Iran has utilised its refugee policy to influence Afghan policy, and counter developments perceived as contrary to its strategic objectives.

Third, the US and European Union's (EU) economic sanctions on Iran have affected both Afghan refugees and humanitarian operations in the country.⁵³ The economic hardship increased social tension and increased negative perception of Afghan refugees among Iranians, particularly the middle, and lower classes who deemed Afghans responsible for low income and unemployment.⁵⁴

The return governance in Iran is informed by security, cultural, political, and socio-economic factors at macro, meso and micro levels. In other words, Iran's decision, process, and responses to return migration have always remained highly political. At the macro level, Iran's relations with international and regional actors including geopolitics, and bilateral ties with Afghanistan have played a key role in determining Iran's return migration governance. At the meso level institutional settings, political structure, statutory provision, and legal frameworks play key roles in shaping Iran's return migration policies. At the micro level societal setting, and cultural values become decisive elements in determining whether states accept refugee influx into local communities or return them back to Afghanistan. As a result, both structural and social elements remain key factors structuring Iran's return migration governance.

4. Findings

Characteristics of return migration governance from Iran to Afghanistan

Iran's restrictive policies began after the fall of the last Soviet-backed communist regime in Afghanistan in 1992. Return initiatives started with the registration of Afghan asylum seekers in preparation for their return to Afghanistan. The policies adopted to support and expedite the return of Afghan asylum seekers included the imposition of restrictions on the provision

⁵²See Christensen, J. B. (2016), 'Guests of Trash', Iran's Precarious Policies Towards the Afghan Refugees in the Wake of Sanctions and Regional Wars,' *Danish Institute for International Studies*, p.16.

⁵³ Christensen,(2016),pp. 23-25

⁵⁴ Christensen (2016), p.25.

of social services such as education, healthcare, and access to the labour market.⁵⁵ In other words, different factors with varying degrees of intensity determined the number of returns from Iran to Afghanistan.

Social tensions against the refugees, largely influenced by Iran's relationship with Afghanistan, have always been a key factor shaping characteristics of return migration governance from Iran to Afghanistan. For instance, a dispute over Helmand water rights has led to political tensions between Iran and Afghanistan. Locals of Sistan and Baluchistan protesting the Kamal Khan Dam in Zabul, Afghanistan, attacked Afghan truck drivers in the country.⁵⁶ Similarly, tension has risen recently between Iranians and Afghans over the mistreatment of Afghan refugees in Iran, which was sparked by the killing of two Shiite clerics at Imam Reza Shrine by an alleged Afghan national.⁵⁷ The exchange of fire between the Afghan and Iranian border guards in Zaranj, Nimruz province, on 27 – 28 May raised tensions between the two countries amid disputes over water rights. Disputes over water rights have long been a political tension that not only remained highly influential in determining social, economic, political, and security relations between the two countries but also had a decisive role in shaping return governance from Iran to Afghanistan.

After every political gridlock between the two countries, Afghan refugees not only become a security concern that shapes Iranian political discourses but also become the top agendas in the mediatic discourses of the country. Reflecting on the water rights stalemates between Iran and Afghanistan, the Aftab (*the Sun*) Newspaper, for instance, published an article on how the deportation of 8 million Afghans can lead to an economic miracle in the country.⁵⁸ Likewise, a member of the Iranian parliament suggested using Afghan refugees as political leverage against the Afghan government over water rights.⁵⁹ As stated earlier, the Iran leadership utilised its refugee policy to influence Afghan policy, and counter developments perceived as contrary to its national interest and strategic objectives.

Socio-political relations between Iran and Afghanistan determine the characteristics of the return migration governance from Iran to Afghanistan. That said, after every political tension, Afghans in Iran are generally left with two options (1) return and (2) outmigration. In other words, recurrent socio-political pressure remains reminiscent for Afghan migrants in Iran that their residence status is not perpetual or long-term. Thus, for a considerable number of Afghan migrants return is the only option against the enduring socioeconomic, political, and psychological hardship in Iran such as persistent ill-treatment, abuse, and humiliation. The primary objective of the Iranian government, as detailed in Section 7.2 and illustrated in Table 3, was to amplify socio-economic pressure on Afghan migrants in order to enforce the policy of return migration. In other words, this strategy was designed to create conditions that would compel migrants to return to their country of origin.

⁵⁵ Abbasi-Shavazi, et al (2005), p.16.

⁵⁶ For detail see Khalid, S. (2022), 'Iran-Afghanistan Tension Over Kamal-Khan Dam', *Hasht-e Subh Daily*, 30 January 2022, <https://8am.af/eng/iran-afghanistan-tension-over-kamal-khan-dam/>

⁵⁷ Sinaee, M. (2022), 'Iran, Afghanistan Tension Rise As Migrant Wave Continues', *Iran International*, 12 April 21, 2022. <https://www.iranintl.com/en/202204123948>,

⁵⁸ <https://aftabnews.ir/fa/news/841622/انجامد80%8E2%ایا-اخراج-۸-میلیون-تبعه-افغانستان-به-معجزه-اقتصادی-می>

⁵⁹ <https://www.afintl.com/202305218265>

Scale and types of return

There are four types of return from Iran to Afghanistan. First, enforced returns, Afghans who are deported due to lack of valid documentation.⁶⁰ Afghans without proper documentation have always been at risk of forced return. In other words, their fate to remain in Iran is determined by socioeconomic situations in the country as well as Iran-Afghan political relations. For example, Iran's Afghan migrant return policies between 1996 and 2001 were influenced by its relations with the Taliban government. In September 1998, the Consulate General of the Islamic Republic of Iran in Mazar-e Sharif was attacked, resulting in the deaths of nine Iranian diplomats⁶¹. This incident significantly strained the relationship between the Taliban and the Iranian government during that period. Between 1998 and 1999 despite sociopolitical, security and economic hardship in Afghanistan Iranian authorities deported about 190,000 undocumented Afghan asylum seekers to Afghanistan.⁶² The continuation of socioeconomic and psychological hardships and increasing migration pressure instigated the Iranian government to return undocumented Afghans to their country. For instance, the enforced returns from Iran to Afghanistan varied from 2,200 in March to over 13,000 in two weeks in August 2022.⁶³

Second, the chain deportation of enforced returns from Türkiye and Europe. Forced returnees from Türkiye are deported by Iranian security officials to Afghanistan from Doghan – Islam Qala and Milak, Zaranj border crossings.⁶⁴ Interviews with returnees from Turkey and Iran (a field survey involving 400 returnees from Iran, Pakistan, and Europe was conducted in Kabul, Mazar-e Sharif, Herat, and Kandahar between December 2023 and January 2024) revealed that not all of the individuals returning from these countries were originally living there. Instead, many were deported from a third country. For instance, a significant number of those identified as returnees from Turkey were actually deported from European countries such as Greece. Similarly, some of those identified as returnees from Iran were, in fact, deported from Turkey. The third type of return from Iran to Afghanistan has been the UNHCR-facilitated voluntary returns since the commencement of the Tripartite Commission with Afghanistan, and the UNHCR in 1992. Between 2020 and 2021 over 1,800 Afghans have voluntarily returned to Afghanistan.⁶⁵ These returnees are Amayish cardholders. While they can stay if they choose to, these cards are subject to renewal, and there is no guarantee regarding when these cards might be terminated.

The fourth type of return migration from Iran to Afghanistan is short-term cyclic returns. Most of the returnees in this category are short-term visa holders and migrants without proper documentation. A considerable number of Afghans return to Afghanistan for a short period of time – cyclic short-term return. The short-term circular returns between Iran and Afghanistan varied in terms of size and socio-demography depending on employment opportunities, family and relative networks and education. For example, a sixty-three-year-old woman from Faizabad district, Jawzjan stated “I have been to Iran several times. I commute to Iran through

⁶⁰ EUAA (2022), p53.

⁶¹ For details see the New York Times report at <https://www.nytimes.com/1998/09/11/world/iran-holds-taliban-responsible-for-9-diplomats-deaths.html>

⁶² Abbasi-Shavazi, M.J., Glazebrook, D., Jamshidiha, G. Mahmoudian, H. and Sadeghi, R. (2005), p.17.

⁶³ EUAA (2022), p54.

⁶⁴ Ibid

⁶⁵ EUAA (2022), p55.

unofficial border crossings depending on security and our economic situation here in the village as well as my daughter and her family's needs."⁶⁶

Existing policies to enforce return

In 2000, the government passed a law, Article 48, that called upon all foreigners, not in possession of work permits, to leave the country by the end of March 2001.⁶⁷ The law also established the Foreign National Executive Coordination Council to deal with the settlement, social services, and deportation of foreigners.⁶⁸ In the same year, the UNHCR agreed with the Iranian government to assist in the repatriation of Afghan asylum seekers although the country during this period was going through acute humanitarian situations.⁶⁹ After the fall of the Taliban and the establishment of a Western-backed interim government in Kabul, in 2002, the Iranian authorities revised their return policy and signed a revised tripartite agreement with Afghanistan and the UNHCR.⁷⁰ Along with these restrictive policies to enforce return migration the Iranian authorities initiated campaigns through media telling Afghans about international aid to Afghanistan opportunities for Afghan migrants to take part in national reconstruction programs, and better economic opportunities in their country.⁷¹ As a result of restrictive policies, UNHCR's material assistance, and government-led mediatic return campaigns, between 2002 and 2005 about 850,000 Afghans returned to Afghanistan.⁷²

In the last two decades, the Iranian government has implemented several preventive policies to encourage and force the repatriation and return of Afghan refugees from Iran. Table 3 summarizes some of the key Afghan refugee policies of Iran that played a significant role in determining migration trends of the Afghan refugees either to return or leave Iran for a third country.

Table 3: Iran's Afghan Refugee Policies Between 2000 and 2022

Date	Policy	Enacted Rules and Regulations
2000	Article 48 Establishment of Foreign Nationals Executive Coordination Council	- Foreigners not in possession of work permits leave the country by March 2001
2001	Prohibition of foreign national employment	- Employment of foreign nationals became subject to a heavy fine - Businesses that employed Afghan refugees were subject to cessation
2002	Tripartite Agreement with the Afghan Government and the UNHCR for the Afghan Refugee Return	- Encourage Afghan refugees to return to Afghanistan - UNHCR provided material assistance to those Afghan refugees

⁶⁶ Interview was conducted with responded in December 2023.

⁶⁷ Abbasi-Shavazi et al (2005), p.17.

⁶⁸ Ibid.

⁶⁹ Christensen (2016), p.11

⁷⁰ Human Rights Watch (2013), p.40.

⁷¹ See Turton, D. and Marsden, P. (2002), "Taking Refugees for a Ride? The Politics of Refugee Return to Afghanistan", *The Afghanistan Research and Evaluation Unit*, p. 2.

⁷² Christensen (2016), p.11

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> who voluntarily opted to return to their country - Return campaign to motivate Afghan refugees to return to Afghanistan
2003	Amayesh Card	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Register all Afghan refugees and Asylum seekers who came to Iran between 1980 and 1990. - Amayesh cards do not provide legal refugee status. - Require regular renewal – each year the card has a different colour and validation periods. - Strict renewal measures, failure to renew the card risk of losing official status and becoming an undocumented Afghan asylum seeker - Renewal costs an annual fee
2003	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulations about Accelerating Afghan Repatriation - Closure of higher education for Afghan refugees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Restriction on hiring Afghans without work permit - Restriction on rent housing for Afghans without documentation - Amayesh cardholders required to give up their card to gain higher education – obtain a student visa
2004	Education fee payment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Afghan refugees had to pay for education
2006	Closure of private school for Afghan undocumented children	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Afghan refugee-run schools for undocumented refugees were terminated
2006	Permission (conditional) for children to apply for Iranian Citizenship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Children of an Iranian mother who are over 18 years old are permitted to apply for Iranian citizenship if the parents' marriage is approved by the state, the applicant is not deemed to have a security threat or criminal background, and the applicant is subject to renunciation of former citizenship.
2006	Restriction for Iranian women to marry Afghan men	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Special permission is required to be able to marry Afghan men - The government refused to accept religious marriages between Iranian women and Afghan men
2007	Declaration No-Go-Areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Several provinces are partially or completely designated as no-go areas for foreigners - No-go areas exist in 28 out of 31 provinces – either partially or completely

		- Afghan refugees are required to obtain written permission to travel to restricted areas
2010	Afghans are forbidden to marry Iranian women	- Marriage between Iranian women and Afghan men is considered illegal
	Implementation of 'Plan for Registering Afghan Nationals' ⁷³	- Registration of undocumented Afghan asylum seekers with the government of Iran - Provision of visa to registered (between 2010 -2012) Afghans with passport
2013	Privatization of <i>Amayish</i> registration. Establishment of Kefalat Centers as private institutions to process <i>Amayish</i> registration	- 166 Kefalat Centers are established across the country
2016	Law on the provision of Iranian citizenship to families of foreign nationals who martyred for the Islamic Republic	- Undocumented Afghan migrants joined the Fatemiyoun military division became illegible to apply for and get permits for residence and citizenship
2017	Headcount of the Undocumented Foreigners ⁷⁴	- Afghan refugees with expired documents and without documents were registered - 804,000 undocumented Afghans were provided with headcount slips, which provided Afghan migrants in Iran a temporary protection
2021	Closed door policy	- Refused to handle additional Afghan refugee burden - Harassment, arbitrary detention and deportation of Afghan migrants

Operational infrastructures of migration and capacity in return governance

Despite statutory provisions on naturalized citizenship (Chapter 3, Article 42) and protection to political asylum (Chapter 10, Article 155),⁷⁵ and being party to the 1951 Refugee Convention and its 1967 Protocol (with reservations regarding Article 17, employment; 23, public relief; 24, labour legislation and social security; and 26, freedom of movement),⁷⁶ Islamic Republic of Iran lacks a comprehensive institutional framework to administer migration issues.

After the Islamic Revolution in February 1979, the first institutional development in terms of migration management was the creation of the Afghan Refugee Coordination Council within

⁷³ For details visit European Union for Asylum's (EUAA) Country of Origin Information on Iran – Situation of Afghan refugees (2022), available at https://euaa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/publications/2023-01/2023_01_COI_Report_Iran_Afghans_Refugees_EN.pdf, p. 18.

⁷⁴ Ibid

⁷⁵ See the Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Iran

⁷⁶ Abbasi-Shavazi et al (2005), p.15.

the Ministry of Interior in the 1980s (see Table 2). As the number of Afghan asylum seekers increased the government of Iran has taken concrete steps to meet the needs of Afghans stuck in limbo by developing institutional infrastructure to manage the Afghan refugee crisis in the country (see Table 2).

As a step towards institutional development, the Executive Coordination Council for Foreign Nationals (ECCFN), chaired by Iran's Ministry of Interior, assumes responsibility for managing various aspects of foreign nationals' affairs, including arrival, residency, deportation, education, employment, and medical care.⁷⁷ The Bureau of Aliens and Foreign Immigrants Affairs (BAFIA), functioning as the operational arm of the Ministry of Interior (MoI), is entrusted with various duties, such as registering asylum-seekers, individually processing asylum applications, and issuing refugee ID cards.⁷⁸ In 2023, BAFIA is replaced by the National Organization for Migration (NOM)⁷⁹

The following chronological account encapsulates the dynamic evolution of institutional frameworks and policy responses shaping the management of Afghan refugees in Iran, highlighting the ongoing efforts to address the multifaceted needs of refugees within the context of shifting socio-political dynamics and humanitarian exigencies.

Table 2: Chronological Evolution of Institutional Frameworks for Afghan Refugees in Iran (1979-Contemporary)*

Year	Institutional Development and Policy Initiatives
1979	Following the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan, Iran experiences an influx of Afghan refugees. Initially, ad hoc measures are implemented to provide basic humanitarian assistance.
1980	Iran establishes BAFIA to manage the growing refugee population.
1980s	With the escalation of conflict in Afghanistan, the number of refugees in Iran swells, prompting the government to collaborate with UNHCR to establish camps along the border.
1990s	The Comprehensive Plan of Action (CPA) is developed, outlining strategies for the voluntary repatriation, local integration, and resettlement of Afghan refugees.
2001	Following the fall of the Taliban regime, a new wave of Afghan refugees enters Iran. The government expands temporary protection measures and allows some refugees to reside in urban areas.
2002	Iran hosts the International Conference on Afghan Refugees, reaffirming its commitment to the humanitarian treatment of displaced Afghans and seeking increased international support.
2010s	Efforts intensify to provide education and vocational training to Afghan refugee children and youth, with a focus on enhancing their long-term prospects for self-reliance and integration.

⁷⁷ EUAA (2022), p. 16

⁷⁸ EUAA (2022), p.17

⁷⁹ For details visit the IOM-Iran webpage at <https://crisisresponse.iom.int/response/iran-islamic-republic-crisis-response-plan-2024-2025>

* The data presented in this table is drawn from various sources cited in the report, including publications from the government of Iran and refugee agencies.

2020	In 2020 the COVID-19 pandemic presents new challenges for refugee management, prompting adjustments in service delivery and support mechanisms to ensure the well-being of Afghan refugees amidst health and economic crises.
2021 - Contemporary	Iran continues to host one of the largest refugee populations globally, with Afghan refugees constituting a significant portion. Despite increasing forced returns and deportation, the government collaborates with UN agencies and humanitarian organizations to provide essential services and pursue durable solutions for refugees.

The evolution of operational infrastructure and its capacity in return migration governance to address Afghan refugee issues in Iran has closely paralleled the shifting political, social, economic, and security dynamics within the country, region and beyond. Over four decades of experience hosting Afghan migrants (*Amayesh* card holders, non-registered and visa holders) has evolved institutional and operational expertise including return migration governance of Iran.

Iran's open-door policy towards the first waves of Afghan influx was not merely due to its *prima facie* policy or sense of obligation to provide protection to Afghan migrants. Rather it was partly because of a lack of institutional capacity, as Iran lacked the required infrastructure to manage the growing number of asylum seekers in the country. As previously mentioned, the influx of over 6,000 refugees from Afghanistan per day between 1980 and 1981 overwhelmed Iran's institutional capacity to effectively manage these irregular arrivals. The table 3 serves as a comprehensive summary of the institutional developments spanning from 1979 onwards, showcasing the responsive adaptations and policy formulations undertaken in tandem with the changing landscape.

Table 3: Institutional Framework for the Management of Refugee Issues

Date	Administrative	Administrative Level	Function
The 1980s	Afghan Refugee Coordination Council	A Coordination Council within the Ministry of Interior	Coordinate the issue of Afghan refugees between the key stakeholders
1989	Bureau for Aliens and Foreign Immigrants Affairs	A bureau under the Ministry of Interior	Management of refugee issues
1991⁸⁰	Law on Employment of Foreign Nationals (National Law on Labour, Social Security and Related Human Rights)	Directorate-General for Employment of Expatriates, Ministry of Cooperative Labour and Social Welfare	Handles employment of foreign nationals other than diplomats and international officials
1950	Social Security Organization	Ministry of Welfare and Social Security, dissolved in 2011. Superseding entity: Ministry of Cooperative Labour and Social Welfare	Provide foreign nationals with national insurance

⁸⁰ For details visit <https://www.ilo.org/dyn/natlex/docs/WEBTEXT/21843/64830/E90IRNo1.htm>

2018	National Migration Organization ⁸¹	Independent Organization	National Policymaking on education, health, property ownership and cultural development of foreign nationals
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The role of the EU as a driving force of return migration governance from Iran to Afghanistan

The EU does not directly dictate strategies or courses of action related to the return of Afghan migrants to their country of origin. The member states of the EU, however, play a significant role through financial support channelled via international migration agencies such as the International Organization for Migration (IOM) and the United Nations Higher Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) in Iran. With this indirect involvement, the EU member states yielded substantial contributions to the governance framework governing return migration processes in Iran. In other words, financial assistance provided by EU member states facilitates the implementation of initiatives aimed at managing and facilitating the return of Afghan migrants, thus exerting a tangible influence on the broader landscape of migration governance in the region. For instance, EU member states like Sweden, Norway, Finland, and Belgium are key financial supporters of various initiatives such as resettlement, pre-departure medical screening programs, Assisted Voluntary Return (AVR) schemes, and the Academy for Migration and Refugee Studies facilitated by the IOM in Iran.⁸²

One of the key driving forces of return migration governance from Iran to Afghanistan is the pushback from the EU to Türkiye and Türkiye to Iran. Türkiye has recently become a country of destination for thousands of irregular migrants from neighbouring countries (notably Syrians), and wider regions fleeing conflicts, and other war-related or environmental constraints. Between January 01, 2024, and April 11, 2024, over 21,000 Afghans were apprehended by Turkish law enforcement agencies.⁸³ Alongside voluntary returns by charter airlines operating from various provinces in Türkiye to Afghanistan,⁸⁴ there are hundreds of thousands of Afghan pushback incidents from Türkiye to Iran.⁸⁵ Moreover, It is observable that while European countries officially suspended the return of rejected Afghan asylum seekers to Afghanistan as the Taliban took over control in August 2021, Türkiye continues to return migrants to Afghanistan. In 2023, a total of 10,260 Afghan migrants were deported to Afghanistan by 20 charter airlines operating from various provinces across Turkey.⁸⁶ It is noteworthy that findings from in-depth interviews with returnees in Afghanistan reveal a significant number of returnees from Türkiye are indeed individuals who have been deported from EU countries to Türkiye.

⁸¹ The National Migration Organization is not fully operational, for details see Moghadam, A., and Jadali S. (2021), p. 30, also visit <https://www.farsnews.ir/news/14010127000177/>-تأسیس-سازمان-ملی-مهاجرت-در-مجلس-کلید-خورد

⁸² For details visit: <https://www.iom.int/countries/iran-islamic-republic>

⁸³ Visit PMM official webpage for updated figures at <https://www.goc.gov.tr/duzensiz-goc-istatistikler>

⁸⁴ Visit Göç İdaresi Başkanlığı (2023) 'Düzensiz göçle mücadelelerimiz ve sınır dışı işlerimiz sürüyor' available at X (twitter) : <https://twitter.com/Gocidaresi/status/1646144658907582469>

⁸⁵ For details see HRW report at <https://www.hrw.org/news/2022/11/18/Turkiye-pushes-afghans-back-iran-border>.

⁸⁶ For detail report published by the Presidency of Migration Management on X: Göç İdaresi Başkanlığı (2023) 'Düzensiz göçle mücadelelerimiz ve sınır dışı işlerimiz sürüyor' available at X (twitter) : <https://twitter.com/Gocidaresi/status/1646144658907582469>

The Presidency of Migration Management is the only authority in the registration and provision of identity cards that enable asylum seekers to access essential social services such as education, public healthcare, and humanitarian assistance.⁸⁷ However, the majority of Afghans not registered at PMM due to various structural (no access, delay, mobility restriction, rejection) and economic (constant movement to find better job opportunities) reasons, remain exposed to the risk of deportation.

With the recent developments and precarious situations in Afghanistan, Türkiye remains highly concerned about the potential influx of Afghan refugees from Iran. Recently, the President of Türkiye, Recep Tayyip Erdogan, has explicitly stated that “Türkiye cannot handle an additional refugee burden.”⁸⁸ Additionally, to prevent irregular Afghan movements, Türkiye has expedited the construction of a three-meter high wall (started in 2017) on its 295 km border with Iran.⁸⁹ Despite these restrictive measures, the continuation of the humanitarian situation in both Afghanistan and Iran will keep the Afghan refugee figures in Türkiye high for the foreseeable time in future. According to recent reports, the number of registered and unregistered Afghan migrants has reached over 300,000 people in Türkiye.⁹⁰ Recently, Türkiye has also received widespread criticism for its forcible return of undocumented migrants including Afghan asylum seekers to Afghanistan and Iran.

In response to criticism and the growing influx of irregular migrants into Türkiye, Turkish authorities have initiated return dialogues with countries of origin. Major progress in this context was the establishment of the National Assisted Voluntary Return (N-AVR) system in September 2020.⁹¹ The N-AVR is a crucial initiative by the Turkish government to promote the safe returns of irregular migrants to their countries of origin. However, the current return rate (including forced return) remains minimal in comparison to the number of apprehended irregular migrants in Türkiye. To summarise, incidents of pushback from Türkiye to Iran have been playing a significant role in shaping return migration governance in Iran. According to a Human Rights Watch report, tens of thousands of Afghans are routinely pushed back to Iran through land borders every year.⁹² The pushbacks mainly occur when migrants are apprehended while crossing the border from Iran to Türkiye, as well as those intending to move from northeastern and southeastern provinces, such as Van, to Istanbul or Ankara. As noted earlier, a considerable number of interviewees were deported after being apprehended while moving from Van to Ankara or Istanbul.

⁸⁷ See Karadag, S. (2021), ‘Ghosts of Istanbul: Afghanistan at the Margins of Precarity’, *Göç Araştırma Merkezi*, p. 28.

⁸⁸ See Yackley, Ayla Jean (2021), ‘Türkiye will not act as EU ‘warehouse’ for Afghan refugees says Erdogan’, *Financial Times*, 26 August 2021, <https://www.ft.com/content/09abc27e-607c-4d83-8e39-84eaa179565e>

⁸⁹ See The Guardian(2021), ‘Türkiye Reinforces Iran Border to Block Afghan Refugees’, *The Guardian*, 23 August 2021, <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2021/aug/23/Türkiye-reinforces-iran-border-to-block-afghan-refugees>, 24 April 2022.

⁹⁰For details visit <https://www.aa.com.tr/tr/gundem/cumhurbaskani-erdogan-turkiyede-su-anda-emniyet-kayitlarimizda-ve-kayit-disi-300-bin-afganistanli-gocmen-soz-konusudur/2341249>

⁹¹ For details on Türkiye return policy see ICMPD’s report at <https://www.icmpd.org/file/download/50571/file/January%25202021%2520Policy%2520Brief%2520-%2520Türkiye%2520Policy%2520Brief%2520-%2520Irregular%2520Migration.pdf>

⁹² For details see Human Rights Watch report on “Turkey Pushes Afghans Back at Iran Border” at [https://www.hrw.org/news/2022/11/18/turkey-pushes-afghans-back-iran-border#:~:text=\(Ankara%2C%20November%2018%2C%202022,in%20a%20report%20released%20today](https://www.hrw.org/news/2022/11/18/turkey-pushes-afghans-back-iran-border#:~:text=(Ankara%2C%20November%2018%2C%202022,in%20a%20report%20released%20today).

Effects of return migration governance from Iran to Afghanistan

According to the UNHCR's operation data report "in total Iran hosts 4.5 million forcibly displaced people of varying statuses which include 750,000 refugees (Amayesh card holders), 2.6 million refugees like population [with the majority of Afghans followed by Iraqis and Syrians], 360,000 resident permit, 267,000 family passport holders and 500,000 undocumented Afghan"⁹³. On the other hand, IOM's Afghanistan cross-border mobility report indicates that between 15 August 2021 and 15 August 2022, the total out-migration from Afghanistan stood at 4.7 million (of which 64% migrated to Pakistan and 36% to Iran) while between 16 August 2022 and 15 August 2023, the number of out-migration recorded was 4.3 million (of which 86% migrated to Pakistan and 14% to Iran).⁹⁴ The number of returnees recorded between 2021 and 2022 was 3.6 million (of which 73% returned from Pakistan and 27% from Iran while the number of returnees between 2022 and 2023 was 4.3 million (81% from Pakistan and 19% from Iran).⁹⁵ It is important to note that these numbers do not reflect the actual numbers given the fluctuation of irregular daily movements in thousands across borders between Afghanistan and Iran⁹⁶.

Empirical evidence indicates (as stated above) that notwithstanding the increasing number of returnees from neighbouring nations back to Afghanistan, the scale of out-migration from Afghanistan eclipses the count of returnees. Despite international praise (for example, Alena Douhan, a Special Rapporteur, in her report stated that "the Iranian government has expressed its commitment to continue inclusive policies,..offering, [Afghan refugees], access to healthcare and education"⁹⁷) of Iranian migration policies by the international community including UNHCR and the Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC)⁹⁸, its return governance to migration remains controversial. To put it differently, the migration governance in neighbouring countries including Iran has proven ineffective, as evidenced by the discernible disparity between the volume of returnees and the magnitude of out-migration over the past three years.

Iran's approach to governing return migration changes in response to various internal and external contextual factors such as domestic socioeconomic conditions (see Sections 6 and 10) and its diplomatic ties with the interim government of Afghanistan. Decisions regarding the returning of undocumented Afghan returnees from Iran to Afghanistan are made on an ad hoc basis, contingent upon the circumstances of the individuals involved⁹⁹. Some are released for personal reasons, while others are detained and compelled to return through irregular crossings, often requiring them to cross fences on the border to return to Afghanistan.¹⁰⁰

⁹³ For details visit UNHCR's online report on the Overview of Iran Operation at <https://data.unhcr.org/ar/country/irn>

⁹⁴ For more about cross-border movement between Afghanistan and its neighboring countries see IOM report on Afghanistan Cross-Border Mobility Report: Two Years of Mixed Migration Review, available at https://roasiapacific.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd1671/files/documents/2024-02/05022023_afg_2y_cross-border-mobility-report.pdf.

⁹⁵ Ibid

⁹⁶ EUAA (2022), pp.51-52; also visit: <https://www.nrc.no/news/2021/november/humanitarian-needs-in-iran-rise-as-300000-afghans-arrive-since-taliban-takeover/>

⁹⁷ For details see Report of the Special Rapporteur on the negative impact of unilateral coercive measures on the enjoyment of human rights, Alena Douhan, at <https://www.ohchr.org/en/documents/country-reports/ahrc5133add1-visit-islamic-republic-iran-report-special-rapporteur>

⁹⁸ EUAA (2022), pp.41-42

⁹⁹ EUAA (2022), pp.50-55

¹⁰⁰ Ibid

Iran's return migration governance technically focuses on the process and ways in which how migrants must be returned to their countries of origin. In other words, like in many countries like EU nations such as Sweden and Greece including Türkiye, return migration governance is politicised and intertwined with domestic concerns. Such return migration governance often prioritises statistical outcomes such as the number of returnees, over long-term solutions aimed at facilitating the reintegration of returnees into their countries of original or habitual residence. For example, the government of Türkiye praised its return governance in 2022, stating that it had successfully deported 109,816 irregular migrants, achieving a deportation rate of 70%, compared to the 10% rate observed in European countries. This high rate was perceived as evidence of Türkiye's effective return migration governance.¹⁰¹ In many countries in the Global North, like the United States, France, and Austria, migrants are often seen as a national security threat. This perception has been a significant theme in electoral campaigns and political discourses, such as those of former US President Donald Trump¹⁰², Norbert Hofer¹⁰³ of the Freedom Party of Austria, and Marine Le Pen¹⁰⁴, the founder of France's National Rally party.

The Afghan government generally responds reactively to Iran's policies on managing the return of Afghan migrants, rather than proactively developing its own policies. Conversely, Iran's approach to return migration is significantly influenced by Afghanistan's policies towards Iran. Thus, the policies of both countries towards each other have a substantial impact on their respective return migration management. As previously noted, (See Page 6), tensions between Iran and Afghanistan, intensified by disputes over water rights, have consistently changed diplomatic relations between the two nations. For instance, protests against the Kamal Khan Dam in Zabul, Afghanistan, resulted in attacks on Afghan truck drivers by locals from Sistan and Baluchistan. These longstanding disputes have had a significant impact on the social (religious and ethnic tensions), economic (bilateral trade), political (water disputes, border matters), and security relations (cross-border exchange of fire) between the two countries, shaping the governance of return migration from Iran to Afghanistan. At the Expert Panel Discussion, convened by Bilim Organization for Research and Social Studies, the Acting Director of Policy Planning at MoRR, Afghanistan affirmed that the Interim Government of Afghanistan is cognizant of the hardships endured by Afghan migrants, including incidents of forced deportations and the infringement upon their fundamental rights by security officials in host nations. Mr. Ahadi emphasized that the Interim Government of Afghanistan maintains a strong commitment to the Refugee Convention and its Protocol. Representatives of the Interim Government of Afghanistan emphasized the following key institutional and macro-level viewpoints:

- The Interim Government of Afghanistan is dedicated to using all available resources to ensure the protection of returnees and to facilitate their reintegration within the country,

¹⁰¹ For details visit the Presidency of Migration Management's official website at <https://www.goc.gov.tr/11-ayda-yaklasik-110-bin-duzensiz-gocmen-sinir-disi-edildi>

¹⁰² For details see Trump Radical Islam Coming 2016, Washington Post, 13 June 2016, https://www.washingtonpost.com/video/national/trump-radical-islam-coming-to-our-shores/2016/06/13/92f9507c-319c-11e6-ab9d-1da2bof24f93_video.html

¹⁰³ See Faiola, A. 2016, "Austria's right-wing populism reflects anti-Muslim platform of Donald Trump", https://www.washingtonpost.com/world/europe/austrias-right-wing-populism-reflects-anti-migrant-anti-muslim-platform-of-donald-trump/2016/05/19/73368bbe-1c26-11e6-82c2-a7dcb313287d_story.html?utm_term=.fffd35bf6393

¹⁰⁴ See Caulcutt, C. (2023) "Marine Le Pen scores big win on toughened immigration bill", *Politico*, <https://www.politico.eu/article/france-marine-le-pen-scores-big-win-on-toughened-immigration-bill-macron/>

- The host nations adhere to international legal frameworks and uphold their obligations under these agreements by affording protection to Afghan migrants.
- The international community should assist the Interim Government in establishing sustainable mechanisms for return and reintegration within the country.

Responding to a question regarding bilateral agreements concerning return and reintegration with the Islamic Republic of Iran, Mr. Ahadi indicated that annual meetings are regularly convened between Afghanistan, Iran and UNHCR to address issues related to return and reintegration. Further, he noted they hold ad-hoc meetings with their Iranian counterparts to address specific migration issues on a case-by-case basis.

With a population of 43 million, of which 37.6 million are living on less than two dollars a day, 30.5 million need social assistance, over 28.3 million have acute humanitarian needs¹⁰⁵, about 6.6 million are internally displaced persons, and over three million are severely affected by drought¹⁰⁶, forced migrations challenges within and outside Afghanistan has increased to unprecedented levels. The number of internally displaced persons (IDPs) has increased from 3.5 million to over 5 million¹⁰⁷ by mid-2021. The stock of Afghan migrants in Iran and Pakistan has dramatically increased since the US and its allies retreat from Afghanistan in August 2021. The number of Afghan migrants in Iran surged from 1 to 1.5 million to 4.5 million (the number of Afghan migrants according to Iranian officials is 5.5 million in the country) in less than two years.¹⁰⁸ Likewise, the number of Afghan migrants has jumped from 1.5 million to 3.7 million in Pakistan.¹⁰⁹

In terms of legal documents, the interim government of Afghanistan has not developed any legal document on any matter let alone migration matters. The situation remains dire, particularly strict religio-cultural codes of conduct and the seclusion of women from social domains including the continuation of the closure of high school and university education for young girls exert long-lasting impacts on individuals to make lifelong migration decisions. With the changing policies and regulations within and outside Afghanistan, mainly the return and externalization policies of receiving countries, out-migration trajectories (routes and patterns) across the national borders have also been equally changing out-migration trends from Afghanistan.

Consequences of regional and international return migration governance on Afghan migration

For the last three decades, the EU has been engaged in externalizing its border control to non-EU states.¹¹⁰ In this context one of the key initiatives has been the EU-Türkiye migration deal that was signed in March 2016. The "EU- Türkiye deal" signed in March 2016 outlines three

¹⁰⁵ See OCHA report at <https://reliefweb.int/report/afghanistan/afghanistan-humanitarian-needs-overview-2023-january-2023>.

¹⁰⁶ NRC (2021), 'Severe Drought Threatens Three Million Afghans.' < <https://www.nrc.no/news/2021/june/severe-drought-threatens-three-million-afghans/>, also see the recent report of IDMC on Afghan IDPs, available at: <https://www.internal-displacement.org/countries/afghanistan/#:~:text=Nearly%206.6%20million%20people%20were,second%20largest%20worldwide%20after%20Syria..>

¹⁰⁷ See Internal Displacement Monitoring Center's report at <https://www.internal-displacement.org/expert-opinion/one-year-on-the-taliban-takeover-and-afghanistans-changing-displacement-crisis>.

¹⁰⁸ <https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/afghanistan>

¹⁰⁹ Ibid.

¹¹⁰ For details on EU externalization policy visit: <https://eu.boell.org/en/secrecy-externalisation-eu-migration#:~:text=For%20at%20least%20three%20decades,controls%20to%20non%20EU%20states>.

main points: Türkiye would prevent irregular migration to Greece, facilitate the return of individuals arriving irregularly from Türkiye, and for every Syrian returned from Greece, EU Member States would accept one Syrian refugee from Türkiye¹¹¹. In return, Türkiye would receive €6 billion to support refugees and visa-free travel for Turkish nationals to Europe.¹¹²

Recently, the European Commission has allocated €220 million to enhance border control at Türkiye's Eastern border, bringing the total EU assistance for refugees in Türkiye in 2022 to €1.235 billion.¹¹³ This funding was part of the additional €3 billion announced in June 2021 to support refugees in Türkiye between 2021 and 2023.¹¹⁴ However, despite the EU- Türkiye migration deal, ongoing reports indicate pushback from EU countries to Türkiye. For example, in 2022, there were 988 pushback incidents from Greece to Türkiye, mainly in the Aegean Sea, involving 26,133 individuals seeking refuge in Europe.¹¹⁵ This marked a 57.1% increase from the previous year, with 65.4% more people sent back compared to the previous year.¹¹⁶ Additionally, Greek border guards pushed back 60% of intercepted boats to Türkiye.¹¹⁷ Likewise, a number of reports indicate pushback from Türkiye to Iran. In November 2022, Human Rights Watch released a report stating that Türkiye regularly pushes tens of thousands of Afghans back through its land border to Iran.

In respond to raising return migration pressure from North to South (EU- Türkiye, externalizing EU border control and pushback) and South to South (Türkiye - Iran, EU border control, building walls, pushback), international refugee and migration regimes such as UNHCR and IOM enhanced their transnational engagements in terms of assisting host government in their approach and management of return migration governance. In informal discussions with officials from international migration agencies in Türkiye, it emerged that IOM- Türkiye plans to send experts to the newly established IOM-Iran office. This aims to enhance capacity in assisting Iranian officials with research and return migration governance, including border management.

At the state level, existing international and regional frameworks impose significant pressure on the Afghan government to accommodate a growing number of returnees, despite its already strained economic conditions, financial limitations, and institutional weaknesses. These challenges include persistent brain drain, dwindling financial resources, and the inadequate presence of female professionals to address the specific needs of women returnees. These constraints not only impede the provision of immediate humanitarian assistance—such as food, shelter, and WASH services—but also undermine efforts toward the long-term objective of sustainable reintegration into local communities.

In-depth interviews with Afghan returnees conducted in January 2024 revealed that a significant number of individuals returned from Iran had initially been deported from EU

¹¹¹ For more information visit: https://www.rescue.org/eu/article/what-eu-turkiye-deal?gad_source=1&gclid=CjwKCAjw3NyxBhBmEiwAyofDYUaH_8CgYgUEw8jaKl7lXXJJcduh1pVonmfAlHJPsyp8_9Dm2UEOhoCeEUQAvD_BwE

¹¹² Ibid

¹¹³ For more on the EU-Türkiye migration deal visit: https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/news/eu-adopts-new-programmes-support-refugees-and-border-management-turkiye-worth-over-eu12-billion-2022-12-12_en#:~:text=The%20European%20Commission%20has%20adopted,socio%2Deconomic%20support%2D%20and%20for

¹¹⁴ Ibid

¹¹⁵ For more information visit: <https://asylumineurope.org/reports/country/turkiye/asylum-procedure/access-procedure-and-registration/access-territory-and-push-backs/>

¹¹⁶ Ibid

¹¹⁷ Ibid

countries to Türkiye and then to Iran and ultimately sent back to Afghanistan. Pushbacks from EU countries and Türkiye frequently trigger further expulsions to Iran, which often culminate in deportation to Afghanistan.

Furthermore, a substantial number of systematic pushbacks have been documented from Greece and Bulgaria to Türkiye and subsequently from Türkiye to Iran, extending a chain deportation process that ultimately leads to Afghanistan. In many cases, the last country of return is recorded as the returnees' final point of return, even when they have spent time in detention centers. As a result, individuals originally expelled from EU countries or Türkiye are often categorized as returnees from their most recent transit country, obscuring the broader dynamics of forced returns.

The persistent deportation and pushback mechanisms, spanning a broad geographical region from Eastern EU countries (Greece, Bulgaria) to Türkiye, Iran, and Pakistan, have been in place for over a decade, profoundly affecting Afghan migrants. These dynamics have compelled many Afghans to engage in self-smuggling, repeatedly navigating irregular migration routes between these destinations over the years.

Impacts of Return Migration Pressure on Return and Reintegration Governance in Afghanistan

There are no specific laws, procedures, or regulations governing the return and reintegration process in Afghanistan. Nonetheless, the Afghan government recognizes the importance of addressing return and reintegration challenges in the country. This includes ensuring socio-economic rights, fostering collaboration between public and international humanitarian agencies working with returnees, promoting justice and good governance. To address these challenges, the Afghan government collaborates with both international and domestic humanitarian organizations to establish the Inter-Ministerial Committee on Refugees, Returnees, and IDPs. This initiative was accompanied by the development of key policies, such as the Comprehensive Voluntary Return and Reintegration Policy, the National Policy Framework for Returnees and IDPs, and the Land Distribution for Shelter to Eligible IDPs and Returnees. These policy frameworks aim to protect and promote the rights of returnees, aligning with both national legislation and international legal standards.

In the Expert Panel Discussion on Afghanistan's Return and Reintegration Policies convened at the Bilim Organization for Research and Social Studies on March 09, 2024, Mr Shukrullah Shakir, the Director of the Department of Return and Reintegration, Ministry of Refugee and Repatriation of Afghanistan, stated that under the framework of the Land Distribution for Shelter to Eligible IDPs and Returnees Program, land parcels are allocated to qualifying returnees, those lacking property ownership.¹¹⁸ Mr. Shakir stated that the government allocates 100 square meters of land per individual within a family unit. For instance, a family of four would receive 400 square meters of land for residential construction. However, the Director acknowledged the various challenges faced by returnees living in these designated areas. These challenges include limited access to essential social services like education and healthcare facilities, as well as limited economic opportunities within the local market.

¹¹⁸ Stakeholder Expert Panel Discussion on Return and Reintegration Policies, March 09, 2024, *Bilim*, available at: <https://www.returnmigration.eu/gaps-news/expert-panel-discussion-on-afghanistans-return-and-reintegration-policies>

In October 2024, Mr. Mahmudul Haq Ahadi, the Director of Policy Planning at MoRR, Afghanistan, along with representatives from the Ministry of Interior and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, visited PMM in Ankara, Türkiye. The purpose of the visit was to discuss the challenges faced by Afghan migrants in Türkiye, including those in detention and removal centers, as well as the operational aspects of NAVR. During the Expert Panel Discussion, Mr. Ahadi stated that a joint technical team had been established between Afghanistan and Türkiye, comprising representatives from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MOFA), MoI, and MoRR, to oversee return and reintegration procedures and processes. These initiatives reflect the mutual willingness of both countries to collaborate in facilitating a healthy return migration process. Nonetheless, institutional challenges, particularly the lack of resources and capacity to effectively manage the return migration and reintegration processes, necessitate Türkiye's consideration of integrating the reintegration process into its Afghan return migration policy. Addressing these challenges will require comprehensive strategies that ensure adequate support systems, resources, and institutional capacities are in place to facilitate the successful reintegration of returnees.

On the other hand, international migration agencies like IOM and UNHCR are essential partners of MoRR in implementing AVR and reintegration programs. Collaborating with MoRR, UNHCR has identified 20 safe zones across ten provinces for return and reintegration.¹¹⁹ UNHCR provides one-time financial assistance for energy, shelter, and entrepreneurship, including \$800 for a solar package, \$3,300 for shelter expenses, and \$800 with an additional \$1,500 for business assets.¹²⁰ Health screenings, vaccination programs, legal aid, and mine risk awareness initiatives are tailored for Afghan nationals repatriated from Iran and Pakistan.

However, strict eligibility criteria must be met for cash assistance, requiring asylum documentation in Iran (Amayesh card) and Afghan Registration Card in Pakistan.¹²¹ These restrictions include those returning from Pakistan before January 1, 2023, are ineligible for cash grants.

Field survey findings reveal structural and procedural challenges in the return and reintegration process. Legal and policy frameworks supporting socioeconomic and property rights of returnees are lacking. The MoRR faces capacity constraints to institutionalize mass return and reintegration processes due to brain drain from political and socioeconomic factors.

5. Conclusion

The recent emphasis of policies in Iran has been on finding a possible solution to enforce return migration to Afghanistan. However, the continuation of humanitarian emergencies in Afghanistan will remain a key push factor and a significant contributor to increasing the number of out-migration from Afghanistan for a considerable time in future. Being the

¹¹⁹ For more information see UNHCR's Report on Priority Areas of Return and Reintegration at <https://reporting.unhcr.org/sites/default/files/Afghanistan-priority-areas-of-return-and-reintegration-August%202020.pdf>

¹²⁰ For more information see UNHCR's Report on Priority Areas of Return and Reintegration at <https://reporting.unhcr.org/sites/default/files/Afghanistan-priority-areas-of-return-and-reintegration-August%202020.pdf>

¹²¹ For details visit <https://help.unhcr.org/pakistan/information-regarding-voluntary-repatriation/care-package-information/>

seventh largest corridor worldwide, Iran will continue serving as one of the key transit routes for hundreds of thousands of desperate Afghans to reach Iran or continue their journey to Türkiye and Europe. Unprecedented increase in the number of Afghan migrants in Iran, in the last few years, is likely to intensify the pressure for irregular migration from Iran to Türkiye in the foreseeable future.

That said, externalisation policies (both North to South and South to South) cannot be successful in face of a continuing humanitarian crisis in Afghanistan. Past academic discussions and policy reports show that effective return requires coordination at macro (between host, and country of origin) at meso (national and sub-national operational levels) and micro level (return and reintegration of migrants). From the returnees' perspective, policies are criticized that they are not returnee oriented. At the macro level, Iran and Afghanistan need to initiate an effective and responsive communication line (technical team) to cooperate on the Afghan return migration from Iran to Afghanistan. In this context, an "International Research and Policy Development Center for Return Migration Governance" can be established between these two countries or at a regional level with country offices in each country.

At the meso level, Iran and Afghanistan should revise and bring reform in existing institutional infrastructure and legal frameworks to better manage the Afghan irregular movements, particularly return and reintegration challenges. This requires refugee oriented structural and operational capacity development at the center and provincial levels. Such initiatives can be strengthened by a bilateral agreement + international and non-governmental units to oversee return migration management from Iran to Afghanistan. At the micro-level, there is a need for migrant-concern-oriented interventions such as identifying key barriers to return. This requires extensive knowledge and information about existing situations in the Iran and Afghanistan. Iran structurally in a better position when compared to Afghanistan, can take a greater role capacitating Afghanistan's institutional skill to strengthen its return and reintegration management.

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